

TIDieR checklist applied to the audio-based engagement guide component

Manuscript: Developing a Place-Based Audio Guide to Support Nature Engagement: Intervention Content and Programme Theory

Scope note: This checklist applies only to the audio-based engagement guide component described in the manuscript. It does not describe the full RESONATE intervention, randomized controlled trial or broader project package.

Guideline source: Hoffmann, T. C., Glasziou, P. P., Boutron, I., et al. (2014). Better reporting of interventions: Template for Intervention Description and Replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide. *BMJ*, 348, g1687. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g1687>

Item	TIDieR item	Component-specific description	Where located / notes
1	Brief name	Audio-based engagement guide component for accessible nature visits. The component consists of place-based audio guidance used during an accessible nature route.	Aim; Methods; Script development
2	Why	The component was developed to support structured engagement with natural environments among adults with mobility impairments by orienting attention, supporting calm sensory engagement and offering reflective, place-based prompts. It was informed by theory and evidence concerning nature engagement, nature connection, emotion regulation, restoration, place attachment and accessibility barriers.	Introduction; Theories and empirical findings informing development; Programme theory
3	Materials	Audio recordings consisting of an introduction and three stop-specific tracks of approximately 7-9 minutes. The content includes guided prompts, reflective narration, pauses/chimes and place-based stories. Delivery requires audio access via smartphone or equivalent playback device, with optional headphones, single-ear listening or loudspeaker mode. The manuscript includes the written scripts/transcripts for the introduction, Air, Trees and Water tracks.	Script development; Figures 3-6; Audio production workflow

Item	TIDieR item	Component-specific description	Where located / notes
4	Procedures	Participants follow a predefined accessible nature route and listen to one audio track at each of three predefined stops. The tracks invite grounding, breathing, sensory noticing, reflection on biological interconnectedness and attention to place-specific nature knowledge. Participants may pause or replay tracks as needed.	Script development; Air/Trees/Water sections; Intervention site
5	Who provided	The guide was developed by an interdisciplinary research team. The script was drafted by the first author and reviewed by the second author. Audio recordings were produced professionally in a recording studio using a soft-spoken, clearly articulated female narrator. During pilot use, participants self-administered the guide, with practical support from the first author/research staff when needed.	Script development; Audio production workflow; Pilot study
6	How	The component is delivered individually, in person, through smartphone-based audio at the nature site. Listening options include headphones, single-ear headphone use and loudspeaker mode. The guide is standardized in content but allows practical flexibility in playback.	Audio production workflow; Pilot study; Refinement of guide and route design
7	Where	The component was designed for use on an accessible 1.2 km nature route in a forest-like arboretum north of Copenhagen, Denmark. The route includes three predefined stops corresponding to the Air, Trees and Water tracks. The site includes parking and accessible toilet facilities, and the route consists mainly of firm compacted soil and gravel, with some sections of reduced accessibility.	Intervention site; Figure 7
8	When and how much	The component comprises one guided nature visit structured around three audio-guided stops. Each stop includes one audio track of approximately 7-9 minutes, plus movement between stops along the 1.2 km route. The full visit includes the introduction, all three tracks and completion of the route at the participant's own pace.	Script development; Intervention site

Item	TIDieR item	Component-specific description	Where located / notes
9	Tailoring	The script content is standardized, but delivery is adapted to participant needs through flexible listening options, including single-ear listening, loudspeaker use, pausing and replaying. Participants may also be accompanied by a helper, family member or service dog, and practical support is available.	Audio production workflow; Intervention site; Refinement of guide and route design
10	Modifications	Pilot and early implementation feedback informed refinements. Background birdsong was added during longer pauses to signal intentional silence and reduce device checking. Listening options were adapted to address sensory interference from headphones. The route was adjusted to improve accessibility, and one story was rewritten to improve prompt-context fit after the route change. No additional guidance was added between stops, to preserve flexibility and spontaneous engagement.	Pilot study; Refinement of guide and route design
11	How well: planned	Fidelity was supported through standardized audio tracks, predefined stops, route marking, professional audio production and research staff availability for technical or practical support. The manuscript does not report a formal fidelity checklist for this component.	Audio production workflow; Intervention site; Pilot study
12	How well: actual	Formal fidelity was not assessed as an outcome. Pilot observations and interviews identified practical delivery issues, including pause uncertainty, headphone-related sensory interference, variation in movement between stops and route/prompt-context fit. These issues informed refinement of the component before further evaluation.	Pilot study; Interaction with technology; Moving between stops; Refinement of guide and route design